

1 **Therapeutic targeting in breast cancer for the treatment of liver metastasis: PDX1.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 Metastasis is the major cause of death from cancer and metastasis to the liver is a frequent complication
7 of both breast cancer and colorectal cancer, among the two most common cancers that afflict man (1-5).
8 We recently utilized whole transcriptome technologies to define the full complement of differentially
9 expressed kinases and phosphatases in HER2+ breast cancer: in the primary tumor, and in metastasis to
10 the CNS (6-8). Here we utilize whole transcriptome technologies (9, 10) to measure total transcription in
11 the liver metastases of humans with breast cancer, comparing the liver metastatic transcriptome to the
12 primary tumor transcriptome. We identify here a therapeutic target based on its differential expression and
13 up-regulation upon metastasis to the liver, PDX1, as a candidate therapeutic target for the medical
14 management of liver metastasis.
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, “regional” metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the liver to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the liver metastatic transcriptome in breast cancer: a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and metastasis-specific, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy: PDX1.

Results

Figure 1: PDX1 is differentially expressed in liver metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

I. Liver metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

n=19 primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

n=16 liver metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
210937_s_at	1.62E-01	-1.426457	-5.32206	-0.4963809	PDX1	3821/22283	82.9

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the breast and in liver metastases of humans with breast cancer (9), we discovered differential expression of *PDX1* in metastasis to the liver in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of *PDX1* changed more than 80% of the human liver metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,283 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of *PDX1* messenger RNA in liver metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of *PDX1* during disease progression and dissemination in breast cancer.

Thus, differential and increased expression of *PDX1* defines the liver metastatic transcriptome in human breast cancer.

Discussion

Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvant chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like trastuzumab). Inhibitors of *PDX1*, immunoglobulin or small molecule based (once evaluated for toxicity and safety) can immediately be tested for efficacy in patients with liver metastasis who have failed previous treatment, with the ultimate goal of identifying the most effective inhibitors of liver metastasis in humans with breast cancer who have not yet progressed but are at predicted high risk, or those whose metastasis has not yet become unmanageable due to metastasis size, number or location. A multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, targeting *CDKN* inactivation and ATP-binding cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance (11).

1 **References**

2

3 1. Tsilimigras, D.I., Brodt, P., Clavien, P.A., Muschel, R.J., D'Angelica, M.I., Endo, I., Parks, R.W.,
4 Doyle, M., de Santibañes, E. and Pawlik, T.M., 2021. Liver metastases. *Nature reviews Disease primers*,
5 7(1), p.27.

6 2. Liu, C., Mohan, S.C., Wei, J., Seki, E., Liu, M., Basho, R., Giuliano, A.E., Zhao, Y. and Cui, X.,
7 2022. Breast cancer liver metastasis: Pathogenesis and clinical implications. *Frontiers in Oncology*, 12,
8 p.1043771.

9 3. Diamond, J.R., Finlayson, C.A. and Borges, V.F., 2009. Hepatic complications of breast cancer.
10 *The lancet oncology*, 10(6), pp.615-621.

11 4. Liu, Y. and Cao, X., 2016. Characteristics and significance of the pre-metastatic niche. *Cancer*
12 *cell*, 30(5), pp.668-681.

13 5. Milette, S., Sicklick, J.K., Lowy, A.M. and Brodt, P., 2017. Molecular pathways: targeting the
14 microenvironment of liver metastases. *Clinical Cancer Research*, 23(21), pp.6390-6399.

15 6. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Increased rate of CNS metastasis in patients with HER2+ breast cancer
16 is a result of the intrinsic gene expression program of HER2+ subtype breast cancers, not a consequence
17 of use of the HER2+-targeted drug trastuzumab.

18 7. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Kinase targeting in HER2+ breast cancer to prevent and treat CNS
19 disease: CDK8.

20 8. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Catalytic site targeting in HER2+ breast cancer for the treatment of CNS
21 metastasis: PPP1R3D.

22 9. GSE124647: Sinn, B.V., Fu, C., Lau, R., Litton, J., Tsai, T.H., Murthy, R., Tam, A., Andreopoulou,
23 E., Gong, Y., Murthy, R. and Gould, R., 2019. SETER/PR: a robust 18-gene predictor for sensitivity to
24 endocrine therapy for metastatic breast cancer. *NPJ breast cancer*, 5(1), p.16.

25 10. GSE56493: Tobin, N.P., Lundberg, A., Lindström, L.S., Harrell, J.C., Foukakis, T., Carlsson, L.,
26 Einbeigi, Z., Linderholm, B.K., Loman, N., Malmberg, M. and Fernö, M., 2017. PAM50 provides prognostic
27 information when applied to the lymph node metastases of advanced breast cancer patients. *Clinical*
28 *Cancer Research*, 23(23), pp.7225-7231.

11. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Therapeutic targeting of catalytically available solid tumor vulnerabilities
in human cancer.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Methods

We utilized GSE124647 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the liver and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with GSE56493 for target validation) using microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods.